

The effect of working at home versus at the office on risk of transmission of SARS-CoV-2 and other respiratory agents – Statistical analysis plan

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This document is an addition to the detailed research protocol [1]. The RCT has been registered in clinical trials (NCT05298488). This document was posted online before the analysis of the data and the unblinding took place.

Trial design

The trial is a two-arm multi-period crossover superiority study where participants (employees of recruited firms) are randomized 1:1 to one of two treatment sequences. Firms and participants within firm may be enrolled and begin treatment at different times (e.g., on a rolling basis during the recruitment period). Figure 1 illustrates the trial timeline and the cross-over structure. Week number is relative to a particular participant’s enrolment rather than trial commencement.

Figure 1: Trial design

Participants will cross-over (change treatment) after four weeks. Week 1 and week 5 will be considered run-in periods. The data collected in these run-in weeks will not be used as outcome data in the statistical analysis.

Plan for reporting and analysis.

We will use the $\alpha = 0.05$ significance criterion throughout. The analysis will be conducted in line with the intention-to-treat principle (ITT), and in accordance with the CONSORT guideline for randomized controlled trials.

The analyst will be blinded to treatment — that is all prespecified statistical analyses will be carried out with treatment sequences (trial arms) coded as ‘AB’ and ‘BA’. Unblinding of the intervention and control groups will be performed only when the analyses are completed. A short, blinded description of results and interpretation will be posted online before blinding is removed. Any analyses that are not prespecified will be reported as exploratory.

We plan to report results in two subsections (discussed further below): (1) Baseline characteristics and recruitment; (2) Main analysis.

1) BASELINE CHARACTERISTICS AND RECRUITMENT

In text and in a CONSORT flow diagram: For each arm, we describe the numbers of firms invited and the number of employees:

- recruited and consented to participate,
- meeting the eligibility requirement,
- randomly assigned to each group,
- receiving intended treatment,
- registering twice, or filling out multiple questionnaires per week (the number of duplicates),
- meeting the compliance criteria and analysed for the primary outcome.

Results of descriptive analyses will be reported as shown in tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: baseline demographic and characteristics for each treatment group.

	AB (n =)	BA (n =)
Female (N, %)		
Age (\bar{x} , SD)		
Status covid-vaccination		
- unvaccinated (N, %)		
- 1. Dose more than 7 days ago (N, %)		
- 2. Dose more than 7 days ago (N, %)		
- 3. Dose more than 7 days ago (N, %)		
- 4. Dose more than 7 days ago (N, %)		
Previously diagnosed with covid-19		
- <5 weeks ago		
Household members (\bar{x} , SD)		
- Children (<18 year) in the households (\bar{x} , SD)		
Participants per firm (\bar{x} , SD)		
Permanent office accommodation (N, %)		
Number of colleagues sharing office		
- Not sharing (N, %)		
- Shared office (2 persons) (N, %)		
- 3-9 persons (N, %)		
- 10 or more (N, %)		
- Other		
Distance to the desk of nearest colleague		
- < 1 meter		
- 1-2 meters		
- > 2 meters		

- Varies, don't know or missing		
Partition wall between the desks (N, %)		
Mean weekly working time at the desk		
- >50% (N, %)		
- <50% (N, %)		
- 0		
- Unknown or missing (N, %)		
Mean contacts at the office per day		
- 0 (N, %)		
- <5 (N, %)		
- 5 or more (N, %)		
- Don't know		

Table 2: Compliance and behavioural outcomes in each treatment group

	AB (n =)	BA (n =)
Compliance, replies on survey per week (\bar{x} , SD)		
Sum days of compliance to the intervention (N, %)		
Time at work		
• Days per week (\bar{x} , SD)		
• Hours per week (\bar{x} , SD)		
Days attending the office per week (\bar{x} , SD)		
Absence days due to sickness per week (\bar{x} , SD)		
In contact with covid-19 pos. persons per week (N, %)		
• at home (N, %)		
• at the office (N, %)		
• in public places (N, %)		
Participants with (any) reported symptoms per week (N, %)		
The work influenced the leisure time of others (4 weeks total)		
• in high degree (N, %)		
• to a small degree (N, %)		
• Unknown (N, %)		
The work was disturbed by others (4 weeks total)		
• in high degree (N, %)		
• to a small degree (N, %)		
• unknown (N, %)		
The working environment/situation was well adapted to perform the tasks (4 weeks total)		
• in high degree (N, %)		
• to a small degree (N, %)		
• unknown (N, %)		
Participants who used public transport per week (N, %)		
Participants visiting restaurants, bars etc. per (N, %)		
Participants attending cultural events per week (N, %)		

2) MAIN ANALYSIS

Primary outcome:

Self-reported respiratory disease:

During the trial, participants will be asked whether they had experienced symptoms of common cold and the degree of illness, or received clinical diagnose or laboratory test confirming a respiratory disease, or experienced any of the following symptoms in the preceding week (airway specific symptoms used in the definition of the primary outcome below are given in parentheses):

- Headache
- Fever
- Blocked or runny nose (airways)
- Reduced sense of smell or taste
- Reduced appetite
- Sore throat (airways)
- Cough (airways)
- Sneezing (airways)
- Body ache or muscle pain
- Exhaustion
- Heavy breathing (airways)
- Stomach ache
- Irritable
- Depressed

On the basis of the list of symptoms we consulted a panel of infectious disease specialists in order to specify how the outcome (a case of a respiratory disease) can be determined. We will classify a participant as having experienced the outcome if they experienced one of the following concurrently:

- 1) Fever + one airway specific symptom (in brackets above)
- 2) Three symptoms (not including fever), where at least one of them is airway specific.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis will account for the trial design as described below. Because firms and employees within firms will be recruited continuously during the trial, we assume that participants may experience different baseline risks of infection with SARS-CoV-2 and other respiratory viruses, corresponding to the time-varying incidence in the general population (figure 2). It is therefore unlikely that baseline risk can be adequately modelled using a constant (intercept term) and must be modelled as an unknown time-varying function.

Figure 2: Description of recruitment and implementation of the interventions within firms and treatment groups over time

We will estimate relative risks using generalized linear mixed-effect models (GLLMs) using an appropriate distribution and link function. We will model the crossover design using a fixed effect for carryover (i.e., previous treatment; a “null” value will be used for the first period in which no carryover is possible) and random intercepts for clustering of outcome measurement within participant. We will model possible intra-firm correlation using random intercepts (i.e., the model's random effect specification will be measurement within participant within firm). We will model the time-varying baseline risk of infection using a fractional polynomial (see below). We will use fixed effects to adjust for the covariates sex (male or female), age (continuous; years), and immune status [2, 3]. Immune status will be measured using two variables. The first is the sum of the number of corona vaccines and the number of registered COVID-19 infections. The second is time since last vaccine/COVID-19 infection (continuous; years). The GLMM, neglecting distribution and link for brevity, is therefore:

$$y_j = \mu + f(t_j) + \alpha_j + \beta_j + \gamma_i + \delta_j + \theta_j + \epsilon_i$$

where y_j is outcome for observation j , μ is grand mean, $f(t_j)$ is baseline risk at time of observation j (see below), α_j is a random effect of firm on observation j , β_j is a random effect of participant in firm on observation j , γ_j is the fixed effect of treatment on observation j , δ_j is the effect of carryover on observation j , θ_j is the fixed effect of the covariates (see above) on observation j , and ϵ_j is the residual effect on observation j . Any collinear covariates will be excluded from the model.

We will model the time-varying baseline risk of infection using a fractional polynomial [4]. Specifically, t_j will identify the time at which treatment started (i.e., start of week 2 or 6; see figure 1) for observation j . Because fractional polynomials are undefined for $t_j \leq 0$, we will define $t = 0$ to be the day before the first participant started treatment, so that all t_j are strictly positive. Because the

fractional polynomials may contain cubic terms (see below), we will measure time in units of years to ensure that f does not take excessively large values.

We will consider fractional polynomials of maximum degree 3, with powers restricted to the set [5 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 3]. This gives rise to a multiplicity of models and therefore a model selection problem. We will choose among models using the approach suggested in the manual entry for the Stata 16 command `fp` (StataCorp LLC, College Station, Texas, USA), as follows. We will identify the model with lowest (i.e., best) deviance among models of degree 1, 2, 3, a model corresponding to $f(t_j) = kt_j$ (i.e., f is linear), and a model corresponding to $f(t_j) = 0$ (i.e., baseline risk does not vary with time and can be modelled by the grand mean, μ). We will then select, and report results for the simplest (e.g., lowest degree) model whose deviance is not statistically significantly larger than the model with lowest deviance overall.

We will visually compare the estimated function f with registry data for Norway (e.g., cases registered in MSIS [Meldingssystem for smittsomme sykdommer]) and assess the estimate for face-validity, although we do not anticipate an exact match because there are important differences between f and numbers of cases. If the estimated function f lacks face validity we will explore other modelling options but will still report the analysis planned herein (e.g., in supplementary materials).

In the unlikely case that all participants within a firm start treatment simultaneously, and firms join the trial at times such that there is little or no overlap between firms' participation, then the random effect at firm level will naturally model the anticipated time-varying baseline risk. In this eventuality we will exclude the fractional polynomial from the model.

While we aim to prevent the occurrence of missing data, if complete data are missing for more than 5% of observations, we will evaluate whether the data are plausibly missing completely at random (MCAR) [6]. If we judge that the data are likely MCAR, we will perform complete case analysis. Otherwise, will we use multiple imputation by chained equations (MICE) [5] using a sufficiently large number of imputations (e.g., 50), and will report any auxiliary variables used.

We will report results as sample prevalences and the estimated relative risks and corresponding risk differences (using an empirical risk of working at the office as a reference), along with 95% confidence intervals (see table 3, below). We will also report intraclass correlation coefficients based on the GLMMs.

Table 3: Results

Primary outcome	AB		BA		A vs. B	A - B
	A	B	A	B	Relative risk (95% CI)	Risk difference (95% CI)
Self-reported respiratory disease	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	RR (95% CI)	RD (95% CI)
Secondary outcomes						
Covid-19 infection (survey)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	RR (95% CI)	RD (95% CI)
Covid-19 infection (registry)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	RR (95% CI)	RD (95% CI)
Covid-19 infection among persons tested (registry)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	RR (95% CI)	RD (95% CI)

Absence-days from work caused by infectious disease, quarantine or other/unknown causes	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	RR (95% CI)	RD (95% CI)
Total number of working days	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	RR (95% CI)	RD (95% CI)
Total work hours	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	RR (95% CI)	RD (95% CI)

Secondary outcomes:

Covid-19 infection based on survey data or register data:

- Positive cases will be those persons who have answered “Yes” to the survey item “Have you tested positive of COVID-19 in the last week?”
- cases notified to the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) with a positive test for covid-19
- cases registered in the MSIS laboratory database with a positive result among all persons in the study population tested for covid-19.

We will analyse and report this outcome using the same model as for the primary outcome.

Absence from work caused by infectious disease, quarantine or other/unknown causes and work hours:

Participants will be asked weekly how many absence-days they had in total in the last week, and of these, how many were caused by illness. In addition, they will be asked if they were diagnosed with or had symptoms related to respiratory infections, and if they had close contact to known COVID-19 positive persons. Finally, participants will be asked how many days and work hours they had in total the last week. We will analyse and report these outcomes using the same model as used for the analysis of COVID-19 incidence based on registry data. We will use the following four event definitions for these analyses:

1. The number of absence-days per group associated with respiratory infections
2. The total number of absence-days for per group
3. The number of absence-days caused by quarantine per group where the days are calculated based on reported contact with known covid-cases and standard quarantine-days advised/ordered by the health authorities
4. The total amount of working-days and work hours per week

References

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